

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: KENYA

Limnological research work at National Museums of Kenya (NMK)

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Fig. 1 Field sampling in various Kenyan aquatic habitats

The National Museums of Kenya (NMK) is a multidisciplinary institution whose mission is to promote the conservation and sustainable utilization of national and cultural heritage through generation, documentation and dissemination of research and collection management knowledge, information and innovations for the benefit of Kenya and the world. The Directorate of National Research and Repository (DNRR) is the research arm of NMK which is vested with the core function of conducting research on the natural heritage of the country as well as collecting and managing the national scientific reference collection.

At NMK our aquatic research work focuses on limnology and marine studies with special emphasis on taxonomy, molecular genetics, ecology and aquaculture of fish, aquatic macro and micro-invertebrates and macrophytes/algae and linking communities with biodiversity research. Fig. 1 shows some field sampling in various habitats. We have a passion for aquatic biodiversity research and conservation based on our academic backgrounds. [Dr. Kochey](#) has a Bachelor of Science degree in Fisheries (1998), MSC in Aquatic Ecology (2013)

and Ph. D in Natural Science-Molecular Biology-Aquatic from J.W. Goethe-University Frankfurt/main, Germany (2018). Ms Joylene has a Bachelor of Science in Botany and Zoology and MSC in Biology, specialization in Human Ecology from Vrije Universiteit Brussels, Belgium.

At NMK we are involved in many limnological research activities across the diverse aquatic environments of Kenya and also globally with a view to documenting species distribution and diversity. Ongoing and recent projects include: Population and conservation status of the endemic and endangered freshwater crab in Lake Chala in Kenya-Tanzania supported by [Mohammed Bin Zayed](#) species conservation (MBZ) grant 2020; the study of natural diet of the fresh water prawn genus *Macrobrachium* for informed aquaculture initiatives and potential use of these prawns in biocontrol of schistosomiasis disease vector snails in Kenya supported by [WIOMSA-MAR-GI grant 2021](#); Mapping the [aquatic biodiversity](#) of the upper Tana river catchment in Kenya supported by The National Conservancy (TNC); Aquatic biodiversity of Mt. Elgon and Cherangani hills in Kenya collaborative project under Kunming Institute of Zoology China (KIZ)/SAJOREC- Chinese Academy of Science; Ecological monitoring of large scale water abstraction/impoundment project: the [Northern Collector Tunnel Phase I \(NCT\)](#) in Aberdare slopes Muranga county; Mapping of disease vector snails in Kenya: Mwea rice fields in Kirinyaga county, [Lake Ol Bollosat](#) in Kenya, Upper river Tana Catchment among others.

Past collaborative international projects we are involved with include: Evolution of [biodiversity of lake Malawi](#); DOI 10.1007/s10750-013-1705-4; DOI 10.1007/s10750-017-3292-2; http://rolschultheiss.weebly.com/uploads/2/1/1/3/21138208/field-school_impulse_02_13.pdf; The Mara Project in Kenya; Aquatic macro-invertebrates and fish the River Mara basin organized by Yale University USA (Cary Institute of Ecosystem studies) funded by the [National Science Foundation](#); <https://mara.yale.edu/news/food-web-short-course>.

We also curate databases of NMK scientific specimen collections as a way of sharing data with other users which is an ongoing activity: Examples include: [Occurrence data](#) of some freshwater crabs housed at NMK. [Species checklist of fresh/brackish water prawns genus *Macrobrachium* in Kenya](#).

We are also involved in [fisheries aquaculture activities](#). <https://www.was.org/meetings/ShowAbstract.aspx?id=136037>. <https://hds.hebis.de/ubffm/Record/HEB440405319>

Other limnological monitoring surveys include updating the [biodiversity Ol Ai Nyiro Nature conservancy](#) in Laikipia Kenya c/o Kuki Gallmann Memorial foundation.

In light of the above Limnological activities, we encourage joint collaborative networks with like-minded international SIL members/peers to build synergies for informed conservation of freshwater biodiversity and habitats.

<https://www.museums.or.ke/>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4889847>